

LHMP: lumped hydrological modelling playground

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ABSTRACT

Providing information about contemporary water resources dynamics for local communities is the one of the major goal for modern hydrology. Tons of scientific papers and engineering reports published each year, but only tiny part of them communicated with society. In this study we present hydrological modelling playground (LHMP) for large Arctic domain. LHMP includes three state-of-art lumped conceptual models for daily runoff predictions, single snow model, required meteorological forcing data, routines for data processing, and set of interfaces (playgrounds) for interaction with results. Playground modules are written in Python programming language and freely available on Github (www.github.com/hydrogo/LHMP).

Keywords: modelling, hydrology, LHMP, Arctic

INTRODUCTION

There were several attempts to make hydrological models available for a broad audience. Seibert and Vis (2012) and Huning and Margulis (2015) developed versions of HBV-light (binary for Windows only) and MOD-WET (set of Matlab functions) hydrological models, respectively, for educational purposes. Andrews et al. (2011) and Irstea modelling group (Coron et al. (2016)) developed R-packages which include wide range of models, routines for model parameters optimization, and visualization tools. These software packages gave a great impetus to hydrological cycle research capabilities, but modelling process still remain difficult for non-professionals because of many difficulties in setting up the programming environment, meeting all packages requirements, stuck in data preparation, etc. Swain et al. (2015) made a comprehensive review of the latest water resources web applications. Most of them provide only data mapping functionality and do not allow the user to operate with data and models independently. Unfortunately, we could find only one example that partially shares our philosophy - Walker and Chapra (2014) developed interactive web-application for water quality modelling.

Our main idea consists of providing to users a browser tab with complete, "batteries included" environment for runoff modelling in selected domain, where they can select river, model, and model parameters on one's own hook. We hope that this interactive playground helps local communities to understand strong complexity of runoff formation processes and find their role in socio-hydrological system.

METHODS

Implementation

LHMP consists of three hydrological models (HBV by Seibert and Vis (2012), GR4J by Coron et al. (2016)), and SIMHYD by Chiew et al. (2002), single snow model (Cema-Neige by Coron et al. (2016)), few auxiliary functions (all written in Python) and core meteorological data (Weedon et al. (2014)) (Figure 1). LHMP uses Jupyter notebooks (jupyter.org) and its widgets as interactive playground. Runoff calculations are hidden from the users, they can select only river basin schematization (three are available by default) and control result by modification of model parameters. Please refer to LHMP Github repository (www.github.com/hydrogo/LHMP) for detailed information.

Operation

You can use LHMP easily on your local machine. Please, follow instructions:

1. Install Docker on your machine - please, refer to the official Docker documentation (<https://docs.docker.com/engine/installation/>);
2. There is a Docker image available to try out LHMP without concerns about the further installation process. To run interactive shell of LHMP (just the Jupyter notebook), please copy-paste following code to your command prompt: `"docker run -d -p 8888:8888 hydrogo/lhmp"`
3. Once started, point a web browser to:
 - `http://localhost:8888` (on Linux);
 - If using docker-machine (Win or Mac users), this will not be `"http://localhost:8888"`. The IP address will be given by tapping in your command prompt: `"docker-machine ip [name-of-your-docker-machine-vm]"`. If you unsure about the name of your docker-machine VM, check the output of the command `"docker-machine ls"`;
 - go to `"interfaces"` folder and use any of the proposed playgrounds.

SUMMARY

Current hydrological decade "Pantha Rhei" is dedicated to support sustainable development of water-humanity tandem. There are a lot of reasons why scientific community should pay much attention to socio-hydrological interaction and provide state-of-art tools for it modelling and assessment. We believe that the first step for progress in this direction is to provide to local communities the opportunity to be involved in scientific research through the use of modern models and techniques for runoff prediction. The LHMP is one of them. Please try to use it for contemporary water resources assessment, flood forecasting, climate change impact studies or identification of the major hydrological processes signatures for the Nadym, Pur, or Taz rivers in Russian part of the Arctic.

SOFTWARE AVAILABILITY

1. Latest source code and software available from: <https://github.com/hydrogo/LHMP>
2. License: GNU GPL v3 (<http://www.gnu.org/licenses/gpl-3.0.en.html>).

COMPETING INTERESTS

No competing interests were disclosed.

GRANT INFORMATION

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REFERENCES

- Andrews, F. T., Croke, B. F. W., and Jakeman, A. J. (2011). An open software environment for hydrological model assessment and development. *Environmental Modelling and Software*, 26(10):1171–1185.
- Chiew, F., Peel, M., Western, A., Singh, V., Frevert, D., et al. (2002). Application and testing of the simple rainfall-runoff model simhyd. *Mathematical models of small watershed hydrology and applications*, pages 335–367.
- Coron, L., Perrin, C., and Michel, C. (2016). *airGR: Suite of GR hydrological models for precipitation-runoff modelling*. R package version 1.0.1.
- Huning, L. S. and Margulis, S. A. (2015). Watershed modeling applications with a modular physically-based and spatially-distributed watershed educational toolbox. *Environmental Modelling and Software*, 68:55 – 69.
- Seibert, J. and Vis, M. (2012). Teaching hydrological modeling with a user-friendly catchment-runoff-model software package. *Hydrology and Earth System Sciences*, 16(9):3315–3325.

- Swain, N. R., Latu, K., Christensen, S. D., Jones, N. L., Nelson, E. J., Ames, D. P., and Williams, G. P. (2015). A review of open source software solutions for developing water resources web applications. *Environmental Modelling and Software*, 67:108 – 117.
- Walker, J. D. and Chapra, S. C. (2014). A client-side web application for interactive environmental simulation modeling. *Environmental Modelling and Software*, 55:49–60.
- Weedon, G. P., Balsamo, G., Bellouin, N., Gomes, S., Best, M. J., and Viterbo, P. (2014). The wfdei meteorological forcing data set: Watch forcing data methodology applied to era-interim reanalysis data. *Water Resources Research*, 50(9):7505–7514.

Figure 1. Conceptual diagram of the LHMP playground